

ComTraForce

REPORT OF A TRACEABILITY CHAIN FOR MULTICOMPONENT FORCES AND MOMENTS

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1. Introduction

This document was created to describe a traceability chain for multicomponent forces and moments.

1.1. Multi-component force sensor

Multi-component force transducers measure forces and/or torques along one or more orthogonal axes in space (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Multi-component force and torque axes

It has generally three different designs:

- Two-component sensors measure compression and tensile forces ($\pm F_z$) as well as the torque M_z that acts on this spatial axis.
- Three-component sensor detects all forces along the three spatial axes x , y and z : compression and tensile forces ($\pm F_z$) and well as thrust and shear forces ($\pm F_x, F_y$).
- The six-component sensors measure all forces ($\pm F_z, F_x, F_y$) plus all torques (M_z, M_x, M_y) along any desired spatial axis.

Multi-component transducers are also referred as multi-"axis" sensors.

A two-axis transducer does not necessarily measure the forces in two orthogonal directions but rather two different measurands (force and torque) along the same spatial axis if necessary.

Multi-component force transducers have many different uses: cutting forces during machining processes, forces and torques during assembly processes with robots, vehicle forces on the road and test bench, forces on wind tunnel balances, monitor screwdriving processes and test bolted joints, etc.

To calculate the forces and moments from the 6 measuring signals, a calibration matrix is required. The calibration matrix establishes the relationship between the 6 measurement signals and the forces F_x, F_y, F_z , and the torques M_x, M_y, M_z .

By using special calibration matrices, you can optimize accuracy and minimize crosstalk for a specific load case.

1.2. Crosstalk

The introduction of a force or a torque in a measuring axis also results in the display in the axes perpendicular thereto. This effect is referred to as crosstalk. In case of three-axis force transducers and multi-component transducers, the crosstalk is approximately 1% of the rated load of the other axes and is proportional to the amount of stress. With increasing lever arms or with larger moments, the deformation of the sensor and the crosstalk increase.

Usually, the calibration takes place in the level of the upper face of the transducers. In contrast to three-axis force transducers, in the case of multi-component transducers, the crosstalk in the

respective operating point can be minimized by calibration at the operating point. By using a second calibration matrix, the crosstalk at this operating point can be reduced to 0.2% to 0.5%. At present, multi-axis calibration is similar to single axis calibration but is carried out once per axis. The calibration of multi-component force sensors is more demanding on the equipment, although the principles remain the same. Measurement of cross talk requires some new considerations. Cross talk is the effect of a calibration force applied along one axis on a different component, for example an output on the x-axis transducer caused by a y-component force. To determine the magnitude of cross talk effects, it may be necessary to construct special purpose calibration machines or fixtures.

2. Traceability Chain

Traceability chain for the multi-component force and torque calibration is given Figure 2.

Figure 2. Traceability for the multi-component force and torque calibration sequence

3. Uncertainty calculation

This proposed draft guideline is intended to give a guidance on the estimation of multicomponent forces and moments measurement uncertainty from calibration laboratory to industrial applications in a range of different areas, namely:

- Uncertainty of forces and moments generated by multicomponent force and moment calibration machines
- Calibration uncertainty of multicomponent force and moment transducers
- Uncertainty of forces and moments measured by multicomponent force and moment transducers in industrial applications.

In each of these cases, the uncertainty determination is based on two major components – the uncertainty obtained during the calibration of the equipment and the uncertainty resulting from the equipment's subsequent use.

4. Determination of the uncertainty of forces and moments generated by multicomponent force and moment calibration machines

Uncertainties associated with multicomponent force and moment calibration machines can be derived in two different paths according to the type of machine. The first type of machines comprehends dead-weight machines able to generate forces and moments usually equipped either with a system of pulleys and bell crank levers or with a system of stainless steel wires, ball

screws and step motors, and hexapod-structured calibration machines equipped with servo motors. Some examples are shown in Fig.3 and Fig.4. Uncertainty associated to these machines can be derived from the uncertainty of the single independent variables or force actuators, similarly to what is prescribed in EURAMET cg-04 v.3 [1] and in literature [2-7].

Figure 3. 6-axis hexapod-structure at PTB and dead-weight 6-axis calibration system at INRIM.

Figure 4. 3-axis calibration system at Kistler

The second type of multicomponent force moment machines are those based on the use of existing uniaxial force standard machines (FSM) integrated with tilted plates, between which the multicomponent force and moment transducer (MCFMT) under calibration is placed, as shown in Figs. 5 and 6.

Figure 5. Scheme of a MCFMT between the 2° tilted plates under the load of the FSM.

Figure 6. 3-D scheme of the forces and moments and top view scheme of the side forces and bending moments generated with the tilted plates on the MCFMT

By modulating the angle of tilt, rotating the transducer around its axis and misaligning it with respect to the machine loading axis, it is possible to decompose the reference force generated by the FSM with the result of generating vertical and side forces and bending and torsion

moments. The relevant equation can be easily obtained from elementary trigonometrical laws as shown in Eq. 1.

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} F_x = F \cdot \sin \alpha \cdot \cos \omega \\ F_y = F \cdot \sin \alpha \cdot \sin \omega \\ F_z = F \cdot \cos \alpha \\ M_x = F \cdot \cos \alpha \cdot \sqrt{d_x^2 + d_y^2} \cdot \sin(i\omega + j\theta) + \frac{F \cdot \sin \alpha \cdot \sin \omega \cdot h}{2} \\ M_y = -iF \cdot \cos \alpha \cdot \sqrt{d_x^2 + d_y^2} \cdot \cos(k\omega + \theta) - \frac{F \cdot \sin \alpha \cdot \cos \omega \cdot h}{2} \\ M_z = F \cdot \sin \alpha \cdot d_y \end{array} \right. \quad (1)$$

Where $\theta = \left| \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{d_y}{d_x} \right) \right|$ and $i=+1, j=+1, k=+1$ for $d_x > 0$ and $d_y > 0$; $i=-1, j=+1, k=-1$ for $d_x < 0$ and $d_y > 0$; $i=+1, j=-1, k=-1$ for $d_x > 0$ and $d_y < 0$; $i=-1, j=-1, k=+1$ for $d_x < 0$ and $d_y < 0$.

Also in this case, the uncertainty associated to the generated forces and moments derives from the uncertainties of the input variables according to GUM (JCGM 100, BIPM) [8] and Prato *et al*, 2022 [9].

5. Determination of the calibration uncertainty of multicomponent force and moment transducers

Similarly to uniaxial force transducers, most of MCFMTs are composed of different outputs, each dedicated to a specific component to be measured. The intrinsic influence between the different components, however, cannot be ignored, and cross-talk signals for combined axial forces and moments must be examined in calibration operations (Fig. 7). Therefore, calibration measurements with various combinations of applied forces and moments are essential for accurately evaluating sensitivity or exploitation matrix terms. According to Ronald Fisher's work from 1926 [10], the calibration experimental plan has a huge impact on the measured sensitivities and related uncertainties. A calibration experimental plan composed of a set of applied forces and moments with high correlations between these components results in a poorly conditioned matrix, which, when inverted, produces poorly defined outcomes with increased uncertainty. As a result, in calibration operations, a suitable experimental strategy connected to the needed level of accuracy and uncertainty must be established. If the lowest level of uncertainty is desired, a full factorial experimental plan with a large number of applied loads should be used, resulting in longer times and higher costs [11]. If higher uncertainties are tolerable, however, fewer measurements can be carried out. Avoiding correlations between variables is also important to satisfy some assumptions behind the calculation and propagation of uncertainty. Since a full factorial experimental plan is usually not applicable, the starting point is the definition of the values for each independent parameter in order to have, at the same time, a feasible number of measurements to be performed and a wide number of combinations to minimize the correlation between the applied components. The main sensitivities and the related cross-talk terms are determined in matrix form, as well as the exploitation matrix, whose terms are the ones used by end-users. Every output of an ideal MCFMT is only dependent on the relevant force or moment component. Actually, this is not true because transducer outputs interact with one another, and cross-talk sensitivities might be important. In first analysis, each force and moment component F_k ($k = 1, 6$) can be expressed as a linear combination of the MCFMT outputs d_i ($i = 1, 6$) with second-order interactions ignored, as shown in Eq. 2 and Eq. 3 in general matrix form.

Figure 7. Uncertainty Model of the force vector transducer calibration

$$\begin{cases} F_x = d_1A_{11} + d_2A_{21} + d_3A_{31} + d_4A_{41} + d_5A_{51} + d_6A_{61} \\ F_y = d_1A_{12} + d_2A_{22} + d_3A_{32} + d_4A_{42} + d_5A_{52} + d_6A_{62} \\ F_z = d_1A_{13} + d_2A_{23} + d_3A_{33} + d_4A_{43} + d_5A_{53} + d_6A_{63} \\ M_x = d_1A_{14} + d_2A_{24} + d_3A_{34} + d_4A_{44} + d_5A_{54} + d_6A_{64} \\ M_y = d_1A_{15} + d_2A_{25} + d_3A_{35} + d_4A_{45} + d_5A_{55} + d_6A_{65} \\ M_z = d_1A_{16} + d_2A_{26} + d_3A_{36} + d_4A_{46} + d_5A_{56} + d_6A_{66} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

$$\mathbf{F} = \mathbf{d} \mathbf{A} \quad (3)$$

where \mathbf{F} is a $1 \times k$ reference forces and moments matrix, \mathbf{d} is a $1 \times i$ matrix of the MCFMT outputs, and \mathbf{A} is a $i \times k$ coefficients matrix, also called exploitation matrix, which is the matrix actually used by end-users. In our case, matrix \mathbf{A} is a 6×6 squared matrix. $A_{i,k}$ are the coefficients of the MCFMT outputs d_i used to calculate the force and moment components F_k . Considering n linearly independent sets of calibration values deriving from the experimental plan, \mathbf{F} and \mathbf{d} , in Eq. 3, become a $n \times k$ and a $n \times i$ matrix, respectively. From simple calculation applied to Eq. 3, matrix \mathbf{A} and its $A_{i,k}$ coefficients can be evaluated according to Eq. 4.

$$\mathbf{A} = [\mathbf{d}^T \mathbf{d}]^{-1} \mathbf{d}^T \mathbf{F} \quad (4)$$

To get an uncertainty directly related to the measured forces and moments, in analogy to ISO 376 for uniaxial force transducers, the matrix \mathbf{A} can be seen as the analogue of the interpolating polynomial in uniaxial force transducer calibrations, the link between the transducer output values (in mV/V) and the force and moment values (in N or N·m). Hence, multiplying the transducer output data d_i by the exploitation matrix \mathbf{A} , forces and moments F_k ($k = 1, 6$) are obtained. These can be treated separately for the calculation of the uncertainty, as if they were six independent transducers, thus taking also into account the cross-talk terms. In this way, it is possible to calculate the uncertainty, one component at a time, similarly to the prescriptions of ISO 376:2011 [12]. From the n calibration conditions, 8 load levels ($j = 1 \dots 8$), 4 positive and 4 negative for each component, repeated 3 times ($m = 1 \dots 3$) in different conditions, shall be selected. Hence, the

combined standard uncertainty of the k^{th} component at a particular j^{th} load level $u_c(F_{k,j})$ can be calculated as

$$u_{\text{cal}}(F_{k,j}) = \sqrt{u_1^2(F_{k,j}) + u_2^2(F_{k,j}) + u_3^2(F_{k,j}) + u^2(\bar{\Delta}(F_{k,j}))} + \bar{\Delta}(F_{k,j}) \quad (5)$$

where $u_1^2(F_{k,j})$ is the variance associated with the applied calibration force or moment found in previous Section. $u_2^2(F_{k,j})$ is the variance associated with the drift in zero output evaluated, $u_2^2(F_{k,j})$ is the same for all j^{th} load levels, $u_3^2(F_{k,j})$ is the variance associated with the resolution of the indicator, $\bar{\Delta}(F_{k,j})$ is the mean deviation from the reference load and $u^2(\bar{\Delta}(F_{k,j}))$ is the variance associated with the mean deviation from the reference load which also contains the contribution due to reproducibility. Term $\bar{\Delta}(F_{k,j})$ can be seen as a systematic error and is treated according to the GUM [8] (note to 6.3.1).

The variance associated with the drift in zero output $u_2^2(F_{k,j})$ is the maximum zero error (converted in N or N·m) obtained from the n calibration measurements according to Eq. (6).

$$u_2^2(F_{k,j}) = \max (F_{k,n} - F_{k,n,0})^2 \quad (6)$$

where $F_{k,n}$ and $F_{k,n,0}$ are the k^{th} force or moment component value acquired during and after the application of the n^{th} calibration force or moment, respectively. $u_2^2(F_{k,j})$ is the same for all j^{th} load levels.

The variance associated with the resolution of the indicator $u_3^2(F_{k,j})$ is the square of the resolution of the indicator (converted in N or N·m) divided by 6, as in Eq. (7).

$$u_3^2(F_{k,j}) = \frac{r^2}{6} \quad (7)$$

where r is the resolution of the indicator according to ISO 376:2011 [12].

$\bar{\Delta}(F_{k,j})$ is calculated as the mean deviation of the three repetitions $F_{k,j,m}$ from the reference applied load $F_{k,j,ref}$.

$$\bar{\Delta}(F_{k,j}) = \frac{\sum_{m=1}^3 (F_{k,j,m} - F_{k,j,ref})}{3} \quad (8)$$

The variance associated with the mean deviation from the reference load $u^2(\bar{\Delta}(F_{k,j}))$ is calculated as the square of the standard deviation of the deviations of the three repetitions $F_{k,j,m}$ according to Eq. (9).

$$u^2(\bar{\Delta}(F_{k,j})) = \frac{\sum_{m=1}^3 \left((F_{k,j,m} - F_{k,j,ref}) - \bar{\Delta}(F_{k,j}) \right)^2}{3} \quad (9)$$

Iterating this process for all components and all levels, the combined calibration standard uncertainty $u_{\text{cal}}(F_{k,j})$ and the expanded uncertainty (at a confidence level of 95 % with a coverage factor equal to 2) $U_{\text{cal}}(F_{k,j})=2u_{\text{cal}}(F_{k,j})$, associated with the k^{th} force and moment component for each j^{th} level, are found. In this way, for each force or moment component, the expanded

uncertainties $U_{cal}(F_{k,j})$ associated with positive-only, negative-only, or both, data can be interpolated with a second-order polynomial function as a function of the applied load F_k . In this way, an expanded uncertainty function associated with each component $U_{cal}(F_k)$ and used by end-users for subsequent operative measurements is found according to:

$$U_{cal}(F_k) = aF_k^2 + bF_k + c \quad (10)$$

6. Determination of the uncertainty of forces and moments measured by multicomponent force and moment transducers in industrial applications

Similarly to the prescriptions EURAMET/cg-04/v.03 document [1], when the multicomponent force and moment transducer is used subsequent to its calibration, the uncertainty in the forces and moments calculated from its displayed values will depend, in part, on its calibration uncertainty, but there are a number of other factors which also need to be considered. These uncertainty sources include, but are not limited to, the following:

- Contribution due to reversibility
- Drift in sensitivity since calibration
- Effect of being used at a different temperature
- Effect of being used with different end-loading conditions
- Effect of being used with a different time-loading profile
- Effect of being used in dynamic conditions
- If applicable, effect of replacement indicator

If it can be assumed that none of these effects are correlated, their standard uncertainties can be summed in quadrature, together with the instrument's calibration uncertainty, to calculate a combined standard uncertainty for each force or moment component, as given in Eq. 11:

$$U(F_k) = \sqrt{\left(\frac{U_{cal}(F_k)}{2}\right)^2 + u_{drift}^2(F_k) + u_{rev}^2(F_k) + u_{TC_0}^2(F_k) + u_{TC_S}^2(F_k) + u_{dyn}^2(F_k) + u_{res}^2(F_k) \dots} \quad (11)$$

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